
School Decision-making Process and Teachers Participation in Educational Policy Implementation in Meme Division, South West Region of Cameroon

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Abstract

Our research study is titled "School decision- making Processes and Teachers' Participation in Educational Policy Implementation." The full participation of teachers in school decision making process, will boost their spirit just for the fact that their ideas also count. These will also bring about teachers' job satisfaction since the school climate is conducive for them to teach and implement all the school policies handed to them by their Principal. Teachers are Nation Builders and they are those to easily and effectively implement all the educational rules and regulations. Given that they have direct contact with the students, they are in the best position to know on what to suggest, which will be of help to the educational sector in general and the students in particular. The principal research question is as follows: "To what extent does school decision- making process influence the participation of teachers in implementing educational policy?". The specific research question are: To find out the extent to which teachers' participation in school meetings influences their implementation of educational policy, to investigate the extent to which teachers' consultations during school meetings influences their implementation of educational policy and lastly, to verify the extent to which delegation of responsibility to teachers during school meetings influences their implementation of educational policy. These questions were then transformed to hypothesis. The methodology adopted a sample survey design with an accessible population of 525 teachers who have taught for at least three years. The sample size was made up of 350 teachers. 350 questionnaires were administered to 20 randomly selected Secondary schools in the Kumba municipality of Meme Division, South West Region of Cameroon. Also, interview guides were administered as the second research instrument to four principals representing the three schools in order to confirm the quantitative data. The data collected was analyzed using the Spearman Correlation Index and multiple regressions. The result obtained shows that there is a positively high relationship between school decision-making process (teachers' participation in school meetings, teachers' consultations during school meetings and delegation of responsibility to teachers during school meetings) and teachers' participation in educational policy implementation; as a determinant from the correlation

index of 0,863. From the above, we conclude that the research maintains the view that the full participation of teachers in school decision-making process will significantly influence the implementation of educational policy. A good number of recommendations were given to the Ministry of Secondary Education, Principals and Teachers. Principals should encourage their teachers by fully involving them in school decision making.

Keywords:

School decision-making Process, Teacher's Participation, Policy Implementation, teachers' participation in school meetings, teachers' consultations during school meetings and delegation of responsibility to teachers during school meetings.

Introduction

School decision-making process is one of the sensitive areas in the school administrative processes. Fonkeng and Tamajong (2009), holds that decision-making is the very heart of the administrative process and leadership. Whatever the leadership behaviour, it involves decision-making, despite whatever the decision is. Effective administration requires rational decision-making which leads to the selection of the best way to reach an anticipated goal. Generally speaking, decision-making involves the process of choosing from among alternative ways of achieving an objective or providing a solution to a problem. It involves choice and entails cost. In fact, decision making is not an end in itself, but a means of achieving organizational goals and objectives. This brings about organizational responses to problems. Decision-making is a major or central responsibility of all administrators, but until decisions are converted into action, they are only good intentions.

Every organization (the school) must make provisions for decision-making. Decisions must be made concerning what goals, purposes, objectives, policies and programmes that will be accepted by the organization as legitimate (Morphet, Johns and Reller, 1982). Decisions need to be rendered continuously with respect to the implementation of policies and programmes. Therefore, every organization, in order to be effective, must have the ability to make decisions. These decisions may be made by the leader, by the group, by the authorities external to the group, or by a combination of methods. Regardless of how decisions are made or who makes them, an organization cannot operate unless decisions are rendered

According to Simon (1976), the effectiveness of organizational decisions could be maximized by increasing the rationality of such decisions. He assumed that there are limits to human rationality and that this creates a need for administrative theory. In the words of Peretomote (1992), the systematic analysis of decision-making is referred to as decision theory. Simon continued to say that two persons, given the same possible alternatives, the same values and the same knowledge, can rationally reach only the same decision". Hence, administrative theory must be concerned with the limits of rationality and the manner in which organization affects these limits for the person making the decision.

Jewell (1998) summed up participative decision making as an effort to avoid the "nobody asked" syndrome. He further explained it to mean soliciting employee's idea for turning the situation in an organization around. He further opined that along with the expectation that asking, will improve the quality of organizational decision making, it is an expectation that people who participate in decisions that affect them will understand the issues better and accept the decisions more readily. Ndu and Anogbo (2007) noted that where teachers are not involved in governance, it results to teachers behaving as if they are strangers within the school environment. Thus, most teachers do not put in their best to have full sense of commitment and dedication to the school.

Mullins (2005) is of the opinion that many people believed that staff participation in decision making leads to higher performance and is necessary for survival in an increasingly competitive world. Welfson (1998) reiterated that boredom and frustration at work is often the result of an employee's lack of involvement in decision making processes with the organization's goals and a feeling that their ideas are not wanted or listened to. He further expatiated that staff turnover increases as employee's walkout of the door for more interesting jobs. Wilkinson (1999), saw involvement of employees in decision making as empowerment while a neglect of employees in decision making was seen as an assumption that workers are untapped resources with knowledge and experience and an interest in becoming involved, employers need to provide opportunities and structures for their involvement. He also assumed that participative decision making is likely to lead to job satisfaction and better-quality decisions and that gains are available both to employers and workers.

Staff cooperation is believed to be an indisputable asset to the school principals while involvement in decision making process by the teachers could ease the principal's mounting problems as many heads would be put together to intellectually solve problems that could have remained unsolved by the principals alone. Shaw (1971) said involving teachers in the decision- making process is like when two men cooperate to roll a stone that neither could have rolled alone. Many administrators express a belief that involvement of teachers in decision making will improve the quality of teacher's decision making in the institution (Collins, 1986). In contrast, where teachers lack motivation and involvement in decision making, truancy, excessive excuses, abstention and complaints usually emerge leading to general ineffectiveness, inefficiency, low productivity and non-achievement of goals of the organization (Awotua-Efebo, 1999).

Okoye (1999), said that workers should be involved in decisions that concern them like general working conditions, fringe benefits and staff development programs as this adds to the attractiveness of the organization climate. Short (1991), emphasized that the kind of school climate that encourages involvement in decision making is characterized by openness and risk taking. This environment encourages teachers to try new ideas and approaches. However, it should be noted that teachers were less willing to participate in decision making if they perceive that their principals sought their opinions but want to

make the final decision rather than allowing teachers that opportunity. Luthans (2005), supported this view that if managers claim to want participation from their people but never let them become intellectually and emotionally involved and never use their suggestions, the result may be negative. Still in line with this view, Emeneke (2004) buttressed the fact that when people are part of decision-making process, there is greater opportunity of the expression of mind, ideas, existing disputes and more occasions for disagreements and agreements.

In some establishments, they are gender biased that women are marginalized in decision making process. United Nations Department of Public information (2006) reported in international women's day that women's participation in high-level economic decision making remains low even in the developed countries, despite educational advances for women in many parts of the world, while women participation in decisions in parliament was said to be 10.99%. It was further reported by the international federation of journalist that although a third of journalists today are women, less than 3% of senior media executives and decision makers are women. Ashton and Webb (1986) found out that those teachers (both male and female) expressed dismay and frustration over their inability to influence the process of decision making. They felt that they were not consulted, irrespective of their ages experience and qualifications and they were made to feel that they could not make good decision. They further reiterated that teachers' self-esteem grows when they feel they are involved in decision making which is something worthwhile and they doing it in a competent manner and that they are recognized for their accomplishment.

Ibukun (1989) observed that teachers in Africa expressed a desire for more involvement in decision making process irrespective of age, experience and qualifications. He further said that agitation by the teachers could reduce conflict in school administration and cause harmony to reign. Teachers feel ownership and commitment of the process when involved in decision making process (Rosenholtz,1985). Nevertheless, the process of decision making and taking to Law and Glover 2000), seems to be problematic for many managers particularly when they are new to the post. While this strategy of making decision taking a shared process may help to promote a stronger sense of 'ownership' and enhance the nature of organizational development, problems can also arise with collective rather than individual manager-led decision making. First, the process can take up much valuable time, and second, issues which in some cases should be settled on a one-to-one basis becomes a collective responsibility- often to the detriment of more important activities. The nature of the decision to be taken is, therefore, important.

It is sometimes suggested that one strategy for resolving such difficulties might be to characterize various decision-types with a typology of decision making. The argument goes that specific procedures could then be applied to assist with the process. The minutes of the staff meetings are typical of the messiness than can arise-leading to a misplaced 'hierarchy of decision making'. For example, there may well be massive concern over small changes to, say, lunch hour arrangements or arrangements for a social function, while highly significant

curriculum delivery arrangements pass by either unchanged or with minimum discussion. Vroom (1974) has stressed the variation in the types of decision made and the need for information systems to back up effective decision-making processes. Although his proposed system appears complex, it is based on assessing the nature or type of decision needed and an awareness of a set of rules. Among the attributes which can be identified in any problem, Vroom includes: the importance of the quality of the decision for organizational development, the extent to which sufficient information is available, the extent to which the problem is structured, the extent to which acceptance by others is critical for success, and the extent to which others will follow a leader. He also contends that the quality of the outcome will depend upon: the rationality of the decision and the acceptability of the decision to others (subordinates').

Teachers participation in school meetings

To Gillett-Swan & Baroutsis (2023) participation of teachers' in school meetings is not just reporting opinions, but is about positioning teachers as empowered participants in shaping educational practice, policy, and decisions that affect their work and students' learning. They argue that valuing teachers' experiential expertise in school discussions such as meetings and committees contribute to meaningful participation beyond token consultations. Their main idea is that teacher participation should be empowering and agentic rather than symbolic. According to Musengamana (2024) teachers generally want meaningful involvement in school decisions especially those affecting classroom practice and school administration and see participation as enhancing collaboration and motivation. However, low participation levels often stem from structural issues like limited opportunities, leadership style, and unclear roles for teachers in meetings and committees. Also, according to the author, teachers value participation in decision-making but face practical barriers.

Moreover, to Macha & Mhagama (2022) teachers' participation in decision-making through meetings and collaborative forums, positively influences their work performance, accountability, commitment, and indirectly student performance. Also, challenges like lack of time, resources, and leadership training can limit teachers' ability to participate effectively. Their key idea is that teacher participation boosts performance but requires supportive conditions. Teachers' participation can dominate the conversation whereas in whole-group settings, researchers or administrators may control the dialogue. This highlights how structure, facilitation, and power dynamics in meetings directly affect teacher participation and voice. (Power & Voice in Research-Practice Partnerships, 2025). A recent policy document emphasises that "teacher voices" are the active participation and influence teachers exert in shaping policies, practices, and decisions that affect their profession. It argues that teacher participation should be recognised formally in governance, curriculum, and school improvement processes to make education systems more responsive and equitable. Teacher participation should be formalized as part of policy and governance (Teacher Task Force Report, 2024)

To Musengamana et al. (2024) teachers are invited to participate in meetings where decisions are made, but actual engagement is limited, teachers sometimes remain silent or are not fully willing to participate. School leaders invite teachers to discuss teaching and learning issues, but teachers are not always integrated meaningfully into conversations about administrative or managerial decisions. More so, Teachers express a desire to be included in decision discussions, especially on issues that affect their professional lives. There is a belief that including teacher perspectives in meetings can produce higher-quality decisions and enhance teacher motivation and satisfaction. However, actual participation varies due to leadership styles and teachers' willingness to speak in meetings.

According to Abonyi (2024) teachers moderately participate in school decision-making through meetings and consultative processes. They are consulted on curriculum, instruction, and school operations, but not consulted on matters such as staffing and financial decisions. Also, teachers are consulted through staff meetings, committees, and school governance structures where they can voice their opinions. Their consultation in meetings is linked to higher organisational commitment and job satisfaction. However, consultation is limited to specific domains, and key areas like finances or admissions are often left to administrators. He emphasizes that consultation is real but selective, often excluding teachers from strategic areas even while involving them in instructional and operational decisions. DeFouw et al (2024) emphasizes that structured consultation with colleagues and specialists, often occurring in school-level meetings, helps teachers express challenges and receive feedback. Informal consultation (such as brief discussions before/after meetings) often yields greater comfort and openness than formal team meetings alone. Teachers, especially less experienced ones, often lack meaningful consultation in planning and policy meetings (Teacher Task Force, 2024).

Delegation of responsibility to teachers during school meetings.

To Kanshabe, Tibanyendera & Tutegyereize (2025) effective delegation by head teachers across administrative and instructional tasks (including meeting-related roles and committee responsibilities) was strongly associated with increased job effectiveness, shared responsibilities, and greater teacher participation in school activity planning and execution. Head teachers delegated tasks such as staff coordination, co-curricular activities, and mentorship, which in turn heightened teacher involvement in school governance and contributed positively to school functioning. Zamudio & Carbonell (2025) in their findings, investigated that although structured delegation of instructional and policy responsibilities remains limited in many schools, where it does occur (e.g., assigning teachers to lead specific decision-making groups or project teams), it tends to support organizational performance, teacher engagement, and shared responsibility in school administration.

Teachers' participation in educational policy implementation.

The reality is that teachers are street-level bureaucrats or front-line implementers that attempt to capture the reality that what teachers and other local implementers ultimately turns out to be when policy is involved. Our understanding of the work of teachers has

become highly nuanced, with teachers viewed not as isolated individuals but as being firmly nested within a complex organization that shapes perceptions, norms and behaviours. Membership in a school community helps develop specific shared ways of making sense of the policies that have to be put into practice, the views held of these policies and the changes that are required (Coburn & Stein, 2006). While some opinions were heard during the peer learning visits presented, teachers as naturally prone to maintaining the status in pursuit of their own interests, other accounts and focus group interviews with teachers helped to highlight the extent to which some teachers implemented policies, particularly when they were given the opportunity to participate in the formulation of reforms or at least give feedback on them.

According to Ronald (2008), in many respects, one can be confident that much talked about policy are having at least some impact at the school level when teachers claim as in one school in Peja (Kosovo) that, compared to the past, they now make more use of project-based and student-centred pedagogies (even if this gave rise to disciplinary problems at times), that they have a better mix between theory and practice, that they feel closer to students, that they use portfolios and other forms of formative assessment strategies, that they plan their teaching more closely with colleagues in subject-based teacher councils, and that rapport with parents has been strengthened. Also, teachers have just a little say in shaping the educational agenda, and their voices are not taken much into account at all, leaving the policy field open to other forces. Lack of consultation with teachers in the reform process is generally detrimental to implementation: ignoring teachers' leads to ignorance about the contexts and conditions in which implementation has to unfold. As a result, even when teachers are positive about change, they end up feeling unsupported when and where it matters most.

More so, teachers interviewed in Kosovo, for instance, noted that while they were all for reform, they were being expected to implement modular curricula without being given the relevant textbooks (Ronald, 2008). They were also expected to take on new curriculum development responsibilities which they had not been previously equipped and resourced to handle and for which they had insufficient time or inadequate rewards. Some teachers were teaching as many as six to nine different curricular programmes in one year. When teacher voices are not heard at the various stages of the policy-making process, anomalies such as these are the order of the day and can spell the death knell of any innovation.

Sabuncuoğlu and Tüz, (1996), the idea behind participation of teachers in educational policy implementation is that in the administration of schools, if principals should involve teachers in the school administrative processes, they will adopt and support the decisions when they actively take part. The goal here is to affect the decisions of the subordinate. On the other hand, there are some factors that limit participation which can be considered as a motivating tool (Eren, 1993). Some of these factors are: Inadequacy of the participants, lack of interest towards the problem, unfair and unsuitable participation of some individuals, and lack of incentives provided by the superiors can be mentioned among these factors

(Bursaloğlu, 1982). Participation in a school environment is both compulsory and more difficult since there are various groups at schools. An administrator who can manage to encourage participation among these groups can regard himself/herself as successful in many regards.

To Motowidlo (1996), participation in school administrative processes by individual teachers in educational institutions may affect many of their behaviours positively and their effectiveness in carrying out their duties. Research has shown that a much higher impact is gained in terms of teaching when the number of teachers participating in the decision-making mechanism at schools is high (Moore & Esselman, 1992). Participation in school administration means extending and anonymizing the authority to make and implement decisions on a specified scale (Eren, 2001), sharing of tasks by the subordinate related to the administration and operation of the institution (Dicle, 1980) and making use of the experiences and professional knowledge of the teacher (Başaran, 1996)

Also, to Bursaloğlu (1982), participation in school administration is also "the undertaking of delegated tasks by each member according to their capacity in relation with the other tasks in an institution composed of interrelated actions". In this sense, participation in school administration gives the teacher the right to participate in the school decision making process, this will increase their zeal to implement the educational policies without any waste of time. Moreover, according to Eren (1993), the full participation of teachers in the school decision making processes will bring about a proper implementation of all the educational policies disposed to them. Teachers' participation in school administration has advantages such as motivating individuals, changing teachers' attitudes and habits, creating a balance between personal goals and institutional goals, generating morale and decreasing resistance and opposition. While full participating in school planning and school decision making processes, will enable teachers to play active roles in decisions that affect themselves and will see to it that such decisions are executed

More so, to Eren (2001), teachers' participation in school decision making, should be undertaken as an activity in which the teachers participating in a decision are valued themselves and their ideas are respected. When teachers believe that they are respected they can express their sincere feelings about innovations and in this way, teachers will feel happy working in the school with their principal while executing their duties for the achievement of the school goals. The act of teachers participating in school decision making processes cannot go beyond a psychological deception used by the administration to enforce feelings and ideas on the subordinate.

According to Freidman (1991), the process of school decision making, planning, directing and organizing should be conducted very carefully and candidly. As a matter of fact, including teachers in making decisions that are related to them may contribute to making healthier decisions. Individuals who participate in decision making in schools are expected to make more sincere efforts to implement those decisions. At the same time, the

administrator aims to affect the decisions of the subordinate by involving them in the process.

The improper implementations of planned activities have been attributed to why there are failures instead of the planning process itself in most circles. Often schools are stripped of funds, basic infrastructures, lack of instructional facilities and even salaries for education staffers are not promptly paid in most developing countries. Strike actions are common phenomenon in these countries. Obviously position of teachers and other staffers are not considered (Chima, 2012). Lack of material and financial resources have jeopardized the education sector that government and philanthropic supports are no more seen, with all these how do we expect the implementation of educational policies to be efficient and effective by teachers who are seen as the sole implementers of all educational policies especially when their voice is not heard and also they are ignored in the planning and decision making processes in the administration of schools in Cameroon.

Lester and John (1948), conducted a classic study on the effects of participation in decision -making, using a series of field experiments at the hardwood manufacturing corporation. The results were clear that subordinate participation in decision- making improved productivity. Hoy and Miskel (1996) supported the desirability and influence of participation of teachers in educational organizations. To these researchers, the opportunity of teachers sharing in formulating policies is an important factor which increases their morale and enthusiasm in the school organization. Participation of teachers in decision- making positively relates to the individual teacher's satisfaction within the teaching profession. Teachers prefer principals who involve them in decision- making and other school administrative processes such as planning, directing and organizing. At times, decisions fail because of poor quality or because they are not accepted by subordinates. The roles and functions of both teachers and administrators in decisions -making needs to be varied according to the nature of the problem.

Nevertheless, according to DiPaola (2007), teachers' levels of participation in school administration (decision making process), should be increased and supported in order to increase the voluntary tasks and altruistic behaviors that go beyond the roles and responsibilities specified in the school organization if really school administrators want teachers to be effective and efficient in implementing their duties in school. Investigation of the relationship between teachers' participation in school administration and the implementation of educational policy shows that the higher the levels of participating in school administration, the higher their implementing behaviours or vice versa.

Ertenü (2008), emphasizes the positive effects of consistency, harmony and integrity in administrative implementations on both empowerment and organizational behaviours. Öz (2008) identified a strong relationship between empowerment and organizational commitment and organizational behaviour. Atalay (2005) suggests that providing teachers with opportunities and a positive climate to work in and appreciating them have a direct

effect on their behaviour in the school institution such as their self-competency and seniority levels and also this will affect their implementation behavior positively. To Aġaoġlu (2002), the role of the school administration defined as the implementation of educational administration in a limited field is to ensure the wellbeing of the school in accordance with its goals by utilizing all available human and material resources at the school effectively. As is the case in all sectors and institutions, the administrators of education and schools who use and ensure the use of all human and material resources are the symbols of productivity and effectiveness processes (Balci, 1993). Therefore, it can be argued that the degree of teachers' involvement in school administrative plan and decisions encouraged by the administrator will show the degree of effectiveness (Moore & Esselman, 1992) and will result in selfless input by the teacher in school.

The implementation of educational policy by teachers will be made very effective if certain opportunities are given to them such as delegating duties to teachers who merit it, consulting them when need be and lastly, involving them in school administrative processes such as school planning process, school decision-making process school organizing process and school directing process since they are the ones who help to facilitate the achievement of good performance and discipline in school. Joint participation of principal and teachers in certain activities within the school organization facilitates the execution of the task easy. Ukeje (1992) opined that "participatory decision-making" improves the quality of decisions, increases the understanding of the group, and also their commitment to the decision. It is very obvious that teacher full participation in school administrative processes will lead to proper implementation of policies and their satisfaction to an extent as they will find the teaching profession prestigious too. The powerful positive results of implementing policies are always hardly achieved. The participation of subordinates in the development and implementation of educational policies, helps to ensure that changes take place faster. Below, we will be laying more emphasis on the teacher, some of his quality and roles.

Teacher

Roe (1989), says that "the quality or effectiveness of a teacher is considered to be associated with his satisfaction towards his profession and his satisfaction with his values". If the teacher is too rigid or has a doctrinaire belief of that his methods are right and those of any one who disagrees with him are wrong, then he will be depriving his children of a range of possible learning experiences, to their disadvantage and to his own. Thus, it is clear that an effective and competent teacher will achieve the desired learning outcome, provided he is satisfied with his profession. But no significant efforts are found to study the competency in relation to job satisfaction among teachers. To Evan (1992), when teachers are motivated not only do the pupils do better in school, but they become motivated about the process of learning, repeating a positive cycle. Lumsden (1998) cited by Evan also state that "when teachers are provided with what they need to remain inspired and enthusiastic in the classroom pupils as well as teachers' will be the beneficiaries". High levels of morale also tend to "motivate, stimulate, encourage, and energize" staff members to do a better job.

Tambo (2012) posits that a teacher is a decision maker since he is the one who carries out planning, implementation, evaluation and feedback. He distinguished two types of teachers which are the effective and the ineffective teachers. An effective teacher is one who uses praise judiciously, he asks questions or gives exercises to ensure that students or pupils follow up the lesson, helps students or pupils apply learning to real life situations. Effective teachers are task oriented and cover the required learning or syllabus more fully than the ineffective teacher. Also, effective teachers use a variety of teaching materials. These include print, graphic audio-visual, electronic materials, as well as models and specimens. Students in effective teachers' classrooms initiate more interactions with teachers than students in the classrooms of ineffective teachers. An Ineffective teacher gives much praises, does not often ask questions and hardly gives exercises to students, that ties with what he is teaching or real life situation and so on. According to Silcock (1993), effective teachers are those that provide students with maximum opportunities.

More so, to Cooper (1986), cited by Smith an effective teacher is seen as one who is able to bring about intended learning outcome or results. If a teacher shows good qualities such as kindness, warmth, enthusiasm, steadiness, alertness, sympathy, but is not able to help students or pupils achieve desirable results he or she cannot be considered effective. In other words, although it is important for teachers to possess such good qualities, it is even more important that they be able to achieve the intended learning results. For teachers to be effective they must acquire and be able to demonstrate certain competencies. Although there is no general agreement about what these competencies are, most authorities in teacher education would agree with the four general competencies listed and explained below (Smith, 1969)

- 1) Command of theoretical knowledge about learning and human behavior
- 2) Display of attitudes that foster learning and good human relation.
- 3) Command of knowledge in the subject matter to be taught.
- 4) Control of technical skills of teaching that facilitate student learning.

Ideal, teacher should be emotionally mature people. However, teachers are human and certainly have their own weakness. It is hoped that with training, they can move ahead from a situation of Immaturity to optimum mental health and maturity. Teachers have four important qualities which are; personal qualities, professional qualities, qualities in relation to children, lastly qualities in relation to the public and children's parents.

The first deals with personal qualities such as being neat, properly dressed, has personality, maintain good health, sincere, patient, honest, impartial, self-confident, courageous, self-control in speech, self-control in emotions, tolerant but consistent, firm, decisive, spontaneous realistic, flexible creative, adaptable to various situations, cooperative, submissive, intelligent, a man of good character, principles, sympathetic, a man with high moral standards, enthusiastic, and kind. Secondly, we talk of professional qualities. In this cases: the individual is supposed to be happy as a trained teacher, has faith in his profession as a teacher, should respect authority, and hierarchy, accept professional evaluation, criticism, be a member of a professional organization, show professional consciousness,

loyalty, be knowledgeable, a good listener, always willing to learn, know his assert, his limitations, strive for competences or excellence, not guilty of very serious speed defects, resourceful, and manifest a love for research

Also, we will talk of the third quality which is the quality in relation to child. The teacher is supposed to love children, respect them, have an unconditional regard for them as individuals, be a disciplinarian, provoke healthy curiosity, be knowledgeable, be able to act in loco parent, be able to get down to the level of the children but yet maintain his self-respect, has the capacity to explain, be able to rise up to the intellectual demands of the children, challenge them even further and beyond, should be a good model, should have interest or excitement in working with children and should be a good story teller. The last quality of a teacher deals with qualities in relation to the public and the children's parents. This quality includes respect for children's parents, should have a good human relation with the public and parents of children, is likeable and is a good citizen (Luma, 1983). From the qualities of a teacher, the next paragraph will be talking about the role of a teacher according to Mbua (2003) and the extensive role of the teacher by Fonkeng and Tamajong (2009).

Theories

Three theories will be used in this work. These theories include; theory Z by William Ouchi (1981), Participative Leadership theory by Likert (1967) and theory of policy implementation by Fullan (2000, 2007, and 2009). Theory Z in School Administration by William Ouchi (1981). According to this theory, decision-making is one of the essential aspects in school administration. This theory recommends the participative and collective approach to school decision-making has it yields more effective implementation than individual decision-making process. Participative decision-making process is one of the mechanisms that provide a broad dissemination of information and values within the organization or institution. Participation of teachers in school decision-making processes in the institution shows a sign of trust and belonging and also involves opinion consideration, communication that is vertical and horizontal means of communication and lastly delegation of responsibilities to those that are willing and deserved it.

Furthermore, there also exist the participative leadership theory by Likert (1967). This theory formulated by Likert suggests that the ideal leadership style is one that takes the input of others into account. Principals are called upon to take into consideration the good ideas of teachers and also allow them to take part in decision making process. These leaders encourage participation and contributions from group members and help group members feel more relevant and committed to the school decision-making process. In participative theories, however, the leader retains the right to allow the input of others. Participative leaders consult others and involve them in the decision-making process. They may make the final decision but in consulting others they are demonstrating consideration, respect for others and the ability to listen. The assumption behind this approach is that it tends to be appreciated by followers who return the favour by being loyal and committed. Participative

leadership also develops other people and builds support for the overall direction, leading to a shared vision and common goals. Participative leaders often also adopt a facilitative leadership style. That is, they empower and encourage others to take and make decisions, take action and act with authority, normally within defined boundaries. Below are some of the assumptions.

- 1) Teachers' involvement in school decision-making improves the understanding of the issues involved by teachers who must carry out the decisions.
- 2) Teachers will be more committed to actions where they are involved in the relevant school decision-making.
- 3) Teachers will be less competitive and more collaborative when they are working on joint goals.
- 4) When the principal and teachers make decisions together, the social commitment to one another is greater and thus increases their commitment to the decision.
- 5) When the principal and teachers decide together, they make better decisions than when the principal decides alone. From the above assumption of this theory it is very clear that if the principal could allow teachers to participate in school decision making: there will be commitment, understanding, collaboration and so forth.

Also, the theory of policy implementation by Fullan (2000, 2007, and 2009). To Fullan, implementation is characterized by complexity, which can create both benefits and risks. Teachers being part and parcel of the decision made know the essence of putting the decision in place and with this; the implementation process becomes easier without any time wastage. According to the implementation theory, one of the conditions for effective implementation to take place is involvement and commitment of staff to decision taken. The theory also made mentioned of three factors affecting policy implementation which are; characteristics of change, local characteristics which took in to consideration other factors including the principal and teacher and finally we have external factors.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers, especially secondary school teachers have always been guidance to students as far as their success and mastery of concepts is concern. No matter who we become in future, each and every one of us will pass through the hands of teachers' So teachers' participation in school administrative processes and the implementation of educational policy will be a major concern to all, as it increases teachers' morale, satisfaction and the academic performance of students. Teachers' participation in school administrative processes and policy implementation is an essential aspect that is not supposed to be reckoned with, if quality output has to be achieved. Their participation in school planning, school decision making, school organization, and school directing processes will bring about their satisfaction and the achievement of educational goal which is that of good performance of students at all level.

Our observation that motivated this research study is that teachers are the sole implementers of educational policies. This made the researcher to embark into research, so as to know if these policies are well implemented or not and the cause. We later discovered the inadequate implementation of educational policies as a result of the passive participation of teachers in key areas in the school administrative processes such as school decision making process. However, it was revealed in the Kumba municipality that the neglect or passive participation of teachers in school decision making process, will affect policy implementation to a larger extent. Carl (2002) and Gauteng Department of Education (1996), affirmed that the "voice" of the teachers is to a large extent ignored or not heard. Teachers are better place to know what to suggest as far as the educational growth of their students is concerned. From the survey carried out in the Kumba municipality in Meme Division South West Region of Cameroon, out of the 350 teachers used as sample population at the level of school decision making process, majority of the respondent 146(42%) and 10(3%) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the fact that teachers opinions count in all areas of the school decision making process. All this aspects will make the implementation of educational policies slow and ineffective. Yigzaw's (1982) carried out a study which indicates that 85% of 110 subjects stated that teachers' had not been involved in the development of curricula. That even at implementation, 63% reported that the most serious problem in this area was that materials were usually not sent on time or that they were not informed of the innovation beforehand.

More so, teachers are the sole implementers of the curricula change but many times they receive little or no orientation on innovation for example today, the world is becoming more computerized than before. So teachers are forced to register student examination marks on the computer, where as many do not know how to operate the computer and so they are liable to make errors in the filling of students' marks in their report cards. In most seminars, the inspectors are to implement innovations without all the necessary equipment needed for a proper implementation to take place (Schnidt and Pramwat, 2006). It is in this light that the study carries out by Özcan's (2010) shows that teachers do not participate in decisions taken and planning process at schools as much as they would like to. The majority of the teachers state that they participate in school decisions and school planning at a lower level however they would like to participate more. Olorunsola (2011) added that for quality and effective implementation of educational policies to occur, it needs the joint effort of both the principal and staff to part takes fully in the school administrative processes. Results of the study carried by Sivri's (2010) display that if administrators could allow teachers to participate in budgetary issues in their institution, this will increase institutional commitment. This is not the case with our secondary school administrators today because budgetary or financial issues are seen as their sole responsibilities that teachers have no say. However, the relationship between institutional behaviour and institutional commitment is not statistically meaningful. Finally, teachers are not happy executing all the duties given to them by their principal due to the period that some of the duties are given that increases their work load.

Research Questions

Main Research Question

To verify to what extent does school decision making process influences Teachers' participation in educational policy implementation?

Specific Research Questions

To find out the extent to which teachers' participation in school meetings influences their implementation of educational policy.

To investigate the extent to which teachers' consultations during school meetings influences their implementation of educational policy.

To verify the extent to which delegation of responsibility to teachers during school meetings influences their implementation of educational policy.

Justification of the study

The inadequate implementation of educational policies by teachers as a result of their passive involvement in school administrative processes simply means that teachers are not fully allowed to participate in the processes of school decision making. Principals' do not allowed teachers to participate fully in school decision making process. The full involvement of teachers in school decision making process will bring about efficient and effective implementation of educational policy in schools as they are part and parcel of the decision made. This will also in turn bring about job satisfaction of teachers in the institution given the fact that they are given the opportunity or the room to contribute their ideas for the growth of the school. This will eventually boost their morals. Participation in school decision making process has advantages such as motivating teachers, changing teachers' attitudes and habits, creating a balance between personal goals and institutional goals, generating morale and decreasing resistance and opposition (Eren, 1993). If teachers are allowed to participate in school decision making, they will play active roles in decisions that affect them and will try their possible best to execute this decision for the good of the institution. The idea behind participation is that individual teachers will adopt and support the decisions when they actively take part in decision making (Sabuncuoğlu andTüz, 1996; Eren, 1993).

The role of school administrator defined as the implementer of educational administration is to ensure the wellbeing of the school in accordance with its goals by utilizing all available human and material resources at the school effectively (Ağağlı,2002). As is the case in all sectors, any educational administrator who ensure the use of all human and material resources brings about an increase in productivity and effectiveness in his teachers (Balci, 1993). Therefore, it can be argued that the degree of teachers' involvement in administrative decisions encouraged by the administrator will improve on the implementation level (Moore & Esselman, 1992) as it will result in selfless input by the staff at school. Emeneke (2004), opined that when teachers are part of the decision- making process, there is greater opportunity for them to express their minds, ideas, existing

disputes and more occasions for disagreements and agreements. Ashton and Webb (1986) found out that teachers expressed dismay and frustration over their inability to influence the process of decision making. Short et al. (1991) said the kind of school climate that encourages involvement in school administrative processes such as decision making and the other processes is characterized by openness and risk taking. This environment encourages teachers to try new ideas and approaches. However, it should be noted that teachers will be less willing to participate in decision making if they perceive that their principals sought their opinions but want to make the final decision rather than allowing them that opportunity.

Also, Luthans (2005), supported the view that if administrators claim to want participation from their people but never let them become intellectually and emotionally involved and never use their suggestions, the result may be negative meaning they will not like to be part and parcel of the school administrative process and also they will execute their duties the way they like. Teachers like any other employee will like challenging opportunities in order to easily grow. Udo and Akpa (2007) asserted that where teachers are adequately involved in decision making process and others school processes, there will be greater commitment and these teachers will adequately support their principal and the realization of the school goal will be made easier. Opposition within the school will be minimized

Glew et al. (1995) called the system participative decision making and sees it as "higher level individual's effort to provide those at a lower level with a greater voice in institutional performance. Ukeje (1992) opined that "participatory decision-making" improves the quality of decisions, increases the understanding of the group, and also their commitment to the decision. Lastly, the implementation process is a collaborative process and it is a call for leaders to fully involve their subordinates in all school processes. More so, the success of teachers in influencing decisions and the substance of these decisions may be crucial in having teachers actually become leaders in schools. Due to this, principals are afraid of allowing teachers to participate fully in key areas in the administration of schools. Teachers influencing the decision-making process for instance shift their participation in the direction of teacher leadership. Benson and Malone (1987) argued that "teachers experienced a high degree of powerlessness which often develop to a high degree of alienation which predisposes them to locate the source of student learning difficulties in the students themselves, or their home background rather than school methodology."

Benson and Malone (1987) believed that research asking about teacher participation in school administrative processes such as decision-making could be improved by asking teachers "about their influence in school decision-making, rather than involvement in school decision-making". While teachers participate in decision-making, their actual influence may be low, or high, that is there is a qualitative difference in participation, which may affect their sense of efficacy, empowerment or alienation. The fact is that even in the small areas that teachers are allowed to partake in decision making, they have little or no influence in certain issues.

Finally, Participation in school administration means extending and anonymizing the authority to make and implement decisions on a specified scale (Eren, 2001), sharing of tasks by the subordinate related to the administration and operation of the institution (Dicle, 1980) and making use of the experiences and professional knowledge of the teacher (Başaran, 1996). Participation in administration is "the undertaking of delegated tasks by each member according to their capacity in relation with the other tasks in an organization composed of interrelated actions" (Bursaloğlu, 1982). In this sense, participation in administration gives the staff the right to participate in the decision-making process. Full participation of teachers in school processes will lead to their empowerment and a sense of belonging. This will eventually foster their desires to be efficient in the implementation process and vice versa. Teachers are humans which if stimulated positively will respond positively and will produce good results and if stimulated negatively will also respond negatively to the given situation.

Methodology

This study is based in the Kumba municipality in Meme division, South west Region of Cameroon. Kumba is made up of three councils and each of the councils is found under a sub-division that is (Kumba 1, II and III. The researcher decided to work in all the three sub-divisions while randomly choosing 20 schools out of the 31 English Secondary Schools in the Kumba municipality. The reason being that the researcher required a particular population of teachers in the area which could easily be gotten only by involving all the three sub-division. The sample survey design was used. This design was chosen and used because one can easily collect data on important ideas about people, their opinion, attitudes, behaviour and lastly their beliefs. It is also concerned with the administering of questionnaire to chosen population of the study who are teachers.

The population of this study comprises of 554 secondary school teachers in the Kumba municipality who have taught for at least three years and above plus four secondary school principals who were interviewed. All giving a population of 558. The sample population of 350 secondary school teachers was gotten from the target population and this sample population comprises of some selected public, private and confessional secondary schools' teachers in kumba. Here, the researcher worked on 20 schools out of 31 secondary schools in the Kumba municipality and a total number of 350 questionnaires were issued to the 20 schools which comprise of public, lay- private and confessional secondary schools in kumba municipality. The schools were; (C.C.C.H.S Kumba, C.C.A.S, Kumba G.B.H.S Kumba, G.B.H.S Mabanda, G.B.H.S Kosala, G.H.S Kake, P.H.S, B.H.S, St J.C.C, D. B.A, Clabic, GEBICOL, V.C.C, G.H.S Malende, G.H.S Kumba-mbeng, G.H.S Nkanilikum, G.S.S Fiango, G.S.S Kang Barombi, J. S.S. and St F.C.). The sampling technique used was the simple random sampling technique. observation, questionnaires and interview guide were used as instruments for data collection. The questionnaires were administered to the teachers while interviews were done to some of the principals within the selected schools in the area.

Table 1. Sample Population (Number of teachers involved in each school).

Name of school	Sample number of teacher	Number of questionnaires given out	Number of questionnaires returned	% returned
C.C.A.S	40	40	40	100
G.B.H.S Kumba	40	40	40	100
G.B.H.S Mabande	20	20	20	100
G.B.H.S Kosala	30	30	30	100
G.H.S Kake	15	15	15	100
G.H.S Malende	10	10	10	100
G.H.S Kumba-Mbeng	20	20	20	100
G.H.S Nkanilikum	15	15	15	100
G.S.S Fiango	10	10	10	100
G.S.S Kang Barombi	10	10	10	100
P.H.S	20	20	20	100
B.H.S	12	12	12	100
St F.C	16	16	16	100
St John	15	15	15	100
V.C.C	12	12	12	100
D.B.A	20	20	20	100
Clabic	10	10	10	100
Gebicol	10	10	10	100
Jemea. C	8	8	8	100
C.C.C.H.S	07	07	07	100
Total:	350	350	350	100

SOURCE: Field work 2025

From the table above, it is observed that 350 questionnaires were distributed and all recollected. This gave a hundred percent rate of return as seen below:

$$350/350 \times 100/1=100\%.$$

Presentation of Data

Figure 1: Distribution showing that the principal accepts only the old and experienced teachers to part take in some key areas in the decision- making process.

Source: Field work, 2025

Participation of teachers in school meetings.

According to the distribution chart above, majority of the respondents 175(50%) and 39(11.1% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively to the item on the questionnaire while 75(21.4%) and 27(7.7%) agreed and strongly agreed respectively that it is only old and experience teachers who are involved in some key areas in school decision making. Those that were uncertain made up a percentage of 10.

It is in this light, talking about participation in school decision making, to Macha & Mhagama (2022) teachers' participation in decision-making through meetings and collaborative forums, positively influences their work performance, accountability, commitment, and indirectly student performance. Lastly, a teacher may be new in a school but that does not mean he or she is not experience in the teaching profession. Most often, the so called old and experience teachers bring more confusion in the institution due to familiarity and longevity. There are some old teachers who think they know more that the principal and so, to them they are accountable to nobody in the institution not even the principal. Some of them are bad examples to the new ones. This is mostly witness in public secondary schools. The fact that majority of the respondents were against this view, it simply means that longevity in an institution is not a guarantee to participate in some key areas in the school decision making process. The most important is the person's commitment and the love the individual has for the growth of the institution.

Figure 2 Distribution indicating that teachers' opinions are considered in all areas of the school decision making process.

Source: Field work, 2025

Teachers' opinions

The pie-chart above shows that 6(1.7%) of the respondents miss the item in the questionnaire. This simply means that the frequency of all the respondent was 344 instead of 350. The respondents who were uncertain made up (17.1%). Minority of the respondent 80(22.9%) and 48(13.7), agreed and strongly agreed respectively to the fact that teachers' opinions are considered in all areas of the school decision making process. Majority of the respondent 146(41.7%) and 10(2.9%) disagreed and strongly disagreed to the item on the questionnaire. To the researcher, it is not in all situations or all area of the school decision making process that the idea of the teacher will count for the simple reason that there are times that due to the nature of the problem at hand it may cause the principal to assemble a meeting or he or she takes the decision alone. For instance, in a case of a recalcitrant student who is of bad influence to others and also the case of staff discipline when a teacher fail to live up to expectation, the principal immediately acts before informing others so as to bring order in the school making it conducive for teaching and learning.

It is in this light that Fonkeng and Tamajong (2009), said that in such a situation, the principal has all right to act by using his/her past experience to solve the immediate problem that may impede the smooth running of the school as an institution of learning. This type of decision falls under what is known as programmed decision.

Figure 3: Distribution chart indicating that during school decision making teachers in the institution meetings, the principal delegate responsibilities only to devoted and experience

Pie-chart distribution indicating that during decision making meetings, the principal delegate responsibilities only to devoted and experience teachers in the institution.

Source: Field work, 2025

Delegation of responsibility by principals.

From the above chart, the respondents agreed with the point of view that the principal delegates responsibilities only to devoted and experience teachers in the institution during school decision making meetings and they had a percentage of 37. Those that disagreed to the above fact had a percentage of 24 being the second highest. The third highest were those that strongly agreed to the statement. Those that either agreed or disagreed to the above statement made up a percentage of 13 while those that strongly disagreed had just 3%. Finally, summing the percentages of agree and strongly agree, we had a percentage of 60 meaning that more than half of the respondents were in support of the fact or statement that during school decision making meetings, the principal delegates responsibilities only to devoted and experience teachers in the institution. To Kanshabe, Tibanyendera & Tutegyereize (2025) effective delegation by head teachers across administrative and instructional tasks (including meeting-related roles and committee responsibilities) was strongly associated with increased job effectiveness, shared responsibilities, and greater teacher participation in school activity planning and execution. principals should not only delegate tasks but also delegate responsibility and commensurate authority in the management of schools to other staff in order to get the job done, and such opportunities can only be given to devoted and experienced teachers.

Inferential Statistics

Research Hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between school decision making process and Teachers' participation in Educational Policy Implementation.

			Teachers participation in Educational policy implementation	School decision Making process.
Spearman's rho	Teachers participation in Educational policy implementation	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,863**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		,000
		N	304	304
	School decision Making process	Correlation Coefficient	,863**	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	
		N	304	344

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

Looking at the correlation coefficient of 0.8 we discover that this index is closer to 1 thus

indicating that there is a significant relationship between the variables that are under study. Alternatively, the p-value of 0.00 is less than 0.05 which is the alpha. The results reveal that the null hypothesis is rejected while the research hypothesis accepted. Based on this we move forward to conclude that there is a significant relationship between school decision making process and teachers' participation in educational policy implementation in the secondary school. Looking at the plot above, we discover that a linear presentation shows observed points around the line thus denoting an association.

Discussion of findings

There is a positively high relationship between school decision-making process (participation of teachers' in school meetings, consideration of teachers' opinion and delegation of responsibilities by principals) and teachers' participation in educational policy implementation. The findings of this work is linked to theory Z by William Ouchi (1981), Participative Leadership theory by Likert (1967) and theory of Policy implementation by Fullan (2000, 2007, and 2009).

This finding gives credence to the view of Gillett-Swan & Baroutsis (2023) who opined that participation of teachers' in school meetings is not just reporting opinions, but is about positioning teachers as empowered participants in shaping educational practice, policy, and decisions that affect their work and students' learning. The more teachers are committed to a particular decision made or taken due to their participation in the decision, the more efficient and accountable they become as far as the implementation of the decision is concern. The findings further confirm the view of Fonkeng and Tamajong (2009), to these authors decision-making is the very heart of the administrative process and leadership. Whatever the leadership behaviour, it involves decision-making, despite whatever the decision is. Effective administration requires rational decision-making which leads to the selection of the best way to reach an anticipated goal. This is made effective through joint participation of teachers and their principal Generally speaking, school decision-making involves the process of choosing from among alternative ways of achieving and objective or providing a solution to a problem. It involves choice and entails cost. In fact, it is not an end in itself, but a means of achieving organizational goals and objectives. This brings about organizational responses to problems. Decision-making is a major or central responsibility of all administrators, but until decisions are converted into action, they are only good intentions. Teachers are the facilitators of all decision made in any institution of learning. Their participation in school decision-making processes will bring about effective implementation of the decision made.

This finding is in line with the views of DeFouw et al (2024) who emphasizes that structured consultation with colleagues and specialists, often occurring in school-level meetings, helps teachers express challenges and receive feedback. Informal consultation (such as brief discussions before/after meetings) often yields greater comfort and openness than formal team meetings alone. Teachers, especially less experienced ones, often lack meaningful consultation in planning and policy meetings (Teacher Task Force, 2024).

Furthermore, the findings hold the point of view of Kanshabe, Tibanyendera & Tutegyereize (2025) who said that effective delegation by head teachers across administrative and instructional tasks (including meeting-related roles and committee responsibilities) was strongly associated with increased job effectiveness, shared responsibilities, and greater teacher participation in school activity planning and execution. Head teachers delegated tasks such as staff coordination, co-curricular activities, and mentorship, which in turn heightened teacher involvement in school governance and contributed positively to school functioning. Also this findings aligns with Zamudio & Carbonell (2025) in their findings, they investigated that although structured delegation of instructional and policy responsibilities remains limited in many schools, where it does occur (e.g., assigning teachers to lead specific decision-making groups or project teams), it tends to support organizational performance, teacher engagement, and shared responsibility in school administration.

Findings according to Ndu and Anogbo (2007) noted that where teachers are not involved in governance, result to teachers behaving as if they are strangers within the school environment. Thus, most teachers do not put in their best to have full sense of commitment and dedication to the school. It is a call for principals to make teachers participate in all the school activities so as to put in their best and have a sense of commitment and belonging to the school. Mullins (2005) is of the opinion that many people believed that staff participation in decision making leads to higher performance which is necessary for survival in an increasingly competitive world. Teachers are in the best position to give suggestions that will help improve on the academic performance of the institution. They interact with student more than any other individual in the school. Teachers' participation in decision making will eventually make the implementation process easier and faster since the implementers who are the teachers are all aware of the policies to be implemented and the necessity of implementing the decisions.

This finding goes in line with Sivri's (2010) study which display that if administrators should include teachers' participation in budgetary matters, this will automatically increase organizational commitment. In our secondary schools in the Kumba municipality and the entire nation in general, principals see budgetary issues as their sole responsibility that need not to be shared with subordinates. From our field work in 2025, it was realized that the operation of human and financial resources in the institutions was looked into by the principal alone but if they can try to make the teachers know the financial aspects of the institution, this will boost teachers' spirit and increase their commitment in so many aspects in the school.

Below are some of the interviews conducted on some principals on the aspect of school decision making process. The different principals A, B, C, and D from the different schools gave their point of view on questions asked on decision-making process. Based on the questions below which states: who are those involve in school decision-making process? Are they old and experienced teachers or devoted and experienced teachers? And whose

opinions are considered during decision-making process? Below are the responses of the various principal.

Principal "A" said most of the decision taken in the class counsel for example is cases of dismiss and stubbornness that are discussed there. He continued by saying that we have administrative meetings where only the principals and the administrators take the decision. There are situations that the principal takes personal or instant decisions for instant situations of violet in school. For instance, when a student fights a teacher. Lastly, they are situations that the decisions are made by the disciplinary counsel. According to principal "B" I involve only devoted and experienced teachers during school decision- making process for the simple reason that they have the love of the establishment at heart. It is not in all areas in the decision-making process that teachers are involved because there are situations that I as the principal personally take decisions or act alone in order to facilitate things.

Still on the same questions on school decision-making process, principal "C" said that involvement in school decision-making is a voluntary process, so everybody can be involved. To me, it is an open process. Most often, new teachers are involved and encourage due to the fact that being new in the school does not mean the individual is new in the field or he or she is not experienced. He added by saying that "the administration is always vigilant with the type of proposals and ideas teachers give. The ideas and proposals given are first of all weighed depending on their objectives before taken them into consideration". Lastly, the ideas of principal "D" were in line with the ideas of the orders.

Conclusion

According to research question one, not only old and experience teachers who are involved in some key areas in school decision making process but all staff. To research question two, teachers' opinion does not count in all aspects of the school decision- making process. Lastly, to research question three, the principal should delegate responsibilities only to devote and experience teachers in the institution during school decision meeting who will be able to do the execution on time.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made: In regards to research question one, the principals should not totally neglect the less experienced teachers in decision making as they also need to be developed on the job. Principals should also attend more workshops and seminars to know how to manage the younger teachers so as to build them up since they will eventually take up the mantle from them later. Furthermore, the principal should make sure that a teacher should not teach a particular class and level for more than 3 years in order to stop the problem of mastering the material of that class and to enable them to carryout research and write their lessons frequently. The reason is this, if teachers are always in the same class, they will see lesson preparation has

waste of time and so continue to give the same notes and knowledge to student year in and year out without any innovation. Teachers should be born and effective teachers, not ineffective teachers and teachers of circumstance. This simply means that they should love their teaching profession and also try to put in their best to improve on the falling standards. Teachers especially old public secondary school teachers should learn to continue giving their principals the respect they deserve, when allowed to be part and parcel of some decision-making meetings in schools. Lastly, teachers should be serious, disciplined and committed to their teaching job and moreover, they should have the growth and the welfare of the students at heart if really they want to partake in school decision making process. In fact, honour should be given to whom honour is due or required

According to research question two, The Ministry of education should organize meetings at least once a year especially at the beginning of the academic year to allow all the teachers' representatives to be part and parcel of the meeting held with inspectors and delegates in order that they can contribute their point of views for the smooth running of the academic year.

Finally, in respect to research question three, Institutional duties should be assigned to all teachers whether new or old and not concentrating on those teachers who are effective and efficient. There are individuals that is only when a task is given to them to perform that they are easily identified or discovered though there are some teachers who always like to hinder themselves. Another reason of attributing a task to all is that some teachers will turn to learn things they never knew at first and this will force them to learn things they never knew at first and this will help improve on their errors. Teachers' involvement in key areas in the school decision making process by principals requires that teachers should be effectively present in school, teachers should respect the school hierarchy as far as the implementation of decision is concerned. Teachers should endeavor to effectively put in place all the decisions taken by the principal before the date limit. Teacher should constantly and effectively prepare their lesson notes. Also, teachers should ensure that they complete their teaching programme each academic year without necessarily rushing over the programme.

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